

Human-centered workplaces in the digital transformation of the semiconductor industry – a step towards high and intelligent automation (HIA)

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Abstract

Establishing human centric work places in highly automated and digitized manufacturing plants is very important to increase productivity and quality. However, after successful automation and digitalization, the human factor is often neglected. But it is mandatory to understand how the digital transformation influences existing work places and what can be done for a continuous improvement. This article describes how working conditions could be improved towards optimal employee-centered workplaces. We introduce a methodology that has been successfully used to conduct a structured analysis of the work places and present employee-centered suggestions and recommendations for action to improve the working environment.

Keywords: human-centered work place, expert interview, digital transformation

Purpose

The semiconductor industry is one of the key industries of our modern world. It provides us with products for autonomous driving, modern electronic medicine applications, security technologies and many products that we need in our daily lives. The production of semiconductors itself is one of the most complex productions, since even before the finished end product often more than 1,000 production steps are necessary just to have created the chips on a raw silicon wafer as a first step in the so-called front-end production. After that, the wafers are usually shipped to a back-end location, where the chips have to be separated by other processes, e.g. by sawing processes, and then the final packaging into the respective package has to be done. Thereafter, the products can be distributed to the customers. an increasing focus

is set on *high and intelligent automation (HIA)*. Furthermore, digitization must be developed in respect to improve data quality in order to ensure motivation, responsibility and transparency of the overall production system. Otherwise – as own experiences in work place analysis are showing – companies' risk to navigate through a “valley of tears” while approaching a higher degree of digitization. Figure 1 shows the so called “valley of tears”.

Figure 1 – The valley of tears of digitization (Digitization can work or fail)

The semiconductor industry is under continuous pressure to reliably deliver products of highest quality and to enable short development and delivery times despite long production cycles. Automation and digitalization have already greatly helped to make these goals possible in recent years. Over the last ten years, the production site of Infineon Dresden Technologies (IFD) has shown how versatile the site has become using the latest technologies from the field of automation. In initial works from 2007 and 2008, the authors demonstrated the importance of automation in production and development processes (Heinrich et al., 2008; S. Keil et al., 2008a, 2008b; Lasch et al., 2008).

Further work was done from 2011 onwards on improving design flows in the semiconductor industry by Keil et al. (2011) and Schneider et al. (2015). During the period from 2010 to 2015, the 200 mm production line was automated to a level of more than 90% by using robots in the clean room during ongoing production. Important economic key figures such as delivery reliability, cycle time and quality were significantly increased as a result, and the competitiveness of the site within the group was raised to a high level. The conversion of the line to the high level of automation naturally also entailed massive changes to the work processes for the employees in production and the surrounding areas.

The improved key performance indicators, e.g. costs, speed and quality from the automation of the 200 mm production were an important basis when the decision was made in 2010 to establish the first worldwide high-volume production for power semiconductors at the Dresden site. The processes for power semiconductors, especially if they are based on thin wafer

technologies, posed a great challenge, which could only be solved by means of new automation methods. In the work of Schneider et al. (2016, 2015), the challenges of automating a 300 mm power factory were presented.

Digitization and the Internet of Things (IoT) were – along and after automation – the next logical step to further increase the competitiveness of factories. Work on automation of repetitive, administrative office processes and the use of modern technologies like blockchain applications was described in a number of articles (Herrgoß et al., 2020; Lohmer et al., 2020b, 2020a; Rank et al., 2016, 2015).

The opportunities and benefits of digitalization have been described by Schneider et al. (2021) and Schneider and Lohmer (2021). After the success of the so called Industry 4.0 hype the success story of the European industry is far from being over. All in all, based on the shoulders of Industry 4.0, the 5th Industrial Revolution is at the gates, paving the way to Industry 5.0 and beyond (European Commission - Directorate General for Research and Innovation, 2021). Industry 5.0 is the next step using the IoT to create sustainable and stable supply chain as well as human centric workplaces. Just like automation, digitalization has a very strong impact on jobs today and in the future. The aim of our research is therefore to investigate the impact of these modern technologies on work places and to derive recommendations for action.

The purpose of this paper is to closely integrate the growing work complexity with the seemingly increasing load and responsibility for the workers. We introduce a methodology for digitization which for the first time inherently supports and enables the transformation of work content by modelling and integrating competencies and mental fitness of the workers – which is becoming a key success factor. From a broader perspective, we may understand this approach as a step from a deterministic worldview (the “block universe”) towards an unfolding universe (the “mind universe”). We discovered the dynamics in updating and exploiting workers’ know-how from within a holistic perspective. The approach of this work is a structured analysis of the work places in a modern semiconductor factory at IFD in areas where the level of automation is high and digitization solutions are already implemented. This is particularly true in the areas of operating and maintenance of the wafer transportation system.

Design/methodology

We applied a social science mixed methods approach including observations, expert interviews and surveys at work places in a modern semiconductor factory at IFD in areas where the level of automation is high and digital solutions are already widely implemented. Thus, the focus areas were the operating and the maintenance of the wafer transportation system.

The approach was based on a comprehensive work place analysis of the selected manufacturing areas in the shift in operating and in the maintenance of the transportation system with the goal to find the opportunities but also the risks related to digitization.

The communication structures in the respective areas were recorded and the individual work processes as well as their status quo have been investigated. Furthermore, the most important information bases were analyzed and which information trigger which respective actions. In addition, it was also considered which information is available on-site and remotely.. The employees in the respective areas were asked about their specific work, data and communication structures, remote capabilities and data security as shown in Figure 2 below.

Beside expert interviews, questionnaires were handed out in the shifts including questions about skills, use of automation and digitization, feedback culture and further work psychological aspects. All the data collected were thoroughly discussed and validated by specific teams.

Out of the obtained results, recommendations for action to optimize the work places were derived, considering the currently available technical possibilities. To conclude, an advanced method of *high and intelligent automation (HIA)* has been thoroughly researched, designed and validated in a real production environment which enhanced the productivity and satisfaction of the employees.

Figure 2 – Framework for development of smart digital workplaces

The research was based on the observation and expert interview methodology. The expert interview is one of the most frequently used methods in empirical social research (Meuser/Nagel 2009: 465). As a rule, expert interviews are goal-oriented and information-focused. The person him- or herself moves into the background, while the knowledge comes to the fore (Liebold/Trinczek 2009: 36f). In a process model described by Misoch (2017), the course of the interview is as follows:

1. Definition of an expert
2. Selection of the experts
3. Guideline
4. Interview conducting
5. Evaluation of data

Following this procedure, the observation and expert interviews were conducted at the semiconductor plant of IFD.

The employees in the respective areas were asked questions, which they could answer voluntarily and anonymously. The questions could be answered at any times when production permitted and no stress situations occurred, ideally during the night shifts.

During the observation and expert interview, 21 questions were asked on the following five main topics (specific tasks, acquisition of data and communication structures, assessment of remote capability and questions on data protection and security issues) and are shown in Table 1 below.

Table 1: Questionnaire

<i>Question 1</i>	<i>What is your job?</i>
<i>Question 2</i>	<i>What are your main tasks?</i>
<i>Question 3</i>	<i>Can you please distribute 100% of the total work among the main tasks you mentioned?</i>
<i>Question 4</i>	<i>Do you occasionally perform any secondary tasks?</i>
<i>Question 5</i>	<i>Which of the tasks you mentioned do you have to perform manually?</i>
<i>Question 6</i>	<i>What percentage of work do these manual tasks represent?</i>
<i>Question 7</i>	<i>Who or what do your work tasks get triggered by?</i>
<i>Question 8</i>	<i>How do you get information to solve emerging problems/tasks?</i>
<i>Question 9</i>	<i>Which source of information do you use most often?</i>
<i>Question 10</i>	<i>Is there any information that you can only perceive here on site (at the production workplace)?</i>
<i>Question 11</i>	<i>How large do you estimate the amount of data you have to process daily at your workplace?</i>
<i>Question 12</i>	<i>Do you always have all the data and information you need to process or solve problems and tasks?</i>
<i>Question 13</i>	<i>How do you estimate the ratio of the supervision effort between 200mm and 300mm production line?</i>
<i>Question 14</i>	<i>With whom do you communicate at the workplace? What means of communication do you use for this and what are the topics covered?</i>
<i>Question 15</i>	<i>Which communication channel do you use most often?</i>
<i>Question 16</i>	<i>Has an office workstation already been set up for your department? If yes, have you already used it and what is your opinion about it?</i>
<i>Question 17</i>	<i>What percentage of your job could you already perform from the office?</i>
<i>Question 18</i>	<i>In your opinion, what is the reason for a 100% implementation?</i>
<i>Question 19</i>	<i>What do you need at your workplace (hardware) to be able to perform your work?</i>
<i>Question 20</i>	<i>Is there anything that disturbs or hinders you in your work?</i>
<i>Question 21</i>	<i>How has your work changed as a result of the advance of automation and digitization?</i>

In the process, 40 interviews were conducted in 2021 with employees in the operating area and 10 additional expert interviews in the maintenance area.

In addition to the expert interview, questionnaires in written form were handed out in the shifts with 15 questions on the following topics:

- Interest in using latest technologies
- Skills in the workplace and training
- Digitization / automation
- Feedback culture
- Security and comfort
- Psychological questions

From the standardized surveys, the questionnaires of 42 employees from operating and maintenance were evaluated descriptively in a first step.

Finally, the data from the work place analyses and the interviews conducted were documented, transcribed and coded to the according categories prescribed by the interview guideline.

They were also evaluated anonymously and the final results were discussed on an aggregate level with the shift employees. All the data collected were also discussed and validated by a team of experts responsible for the work place analyses with the respective supervisors and managers of the different areas. In parallel, written data collection forms, which were made available to the shift employees, were evaluated and supplemented with the interview data.

From the obtained results recommendations for action to optimize the work places were derived, considering the currently available technical possibilities, and these recommendations were also shared with another production site.

Findings

The expert and observational interviews as well as the questionnaires led to several findings in the areas of operating and maintenance. An extensive examination of the workflows in the area of the transportation system helped to discover three main focus topics which could be improved immediately. The first finding was the implementation of a task management system which helped the workers to have more transparency within their work and thus saving time. A second finding was that new trainings were needed especially for new workers. Therefore, a cyber-physical training was established for a better and safer training. Based on the new training, another idea was to use this training to certify the employees in the area by introducing a competence and skill management system. For the operating area, different ideas were derived to improve the existing work and also the fears and needs of the operators in highly automated workplaces.

Some of the results of the anonymous survey conducted to find out more about the wellbeing and satisfaction of the workers in different workplaces inside of the cleanroom are shown in Figure 3 below and described in the following.

Figure 3 – Survey of the employees in a semiconductor factory (motivation of workers)

The results of the interviews showed in a first step that the implementation of factory

automation and digitization has been very well accepted by the workers within manufacturing and maintenance so far. Most of the employees are very interested using new technologies supporting their daily work and they could strongly identify themselves within their daily work. A highlight is, that almost all of the workers would like to be trained on new technologies and stated that they have still a self-determined work in case of highly digitized working places.

Nevertheless, the survey demonstrated that also negative consequences due to higher automation and digitalization are feared by workers in the semiconductor facility. This most common fears of the personnel are displayed in Figure 4 and described in the following.

Figure 4 – Survey of the employees in a semiconductor factory (factors of demotivation)

Around 20% of the workers feel that they can lose the self-determination within their daily work when the work is more and more automated which can lead to a decreasing physical and mental well-being. If robots take over the load and unloading of the production equipment, e.g., the workers are fixed on chairs during their work which lead to negative impacts to the health.

Also, communication and creative exchanges are feared to be influenced negatively.

Digitization can lead on the one side to more monotonous work because the workflows take over the mental work and on the other hand, the stress can be higher due to new software features or situations that are getting more and more complex. The two main fears out of this survey were missing feedback from managers, which leads to a decreasing appreciation of the work of the employees leading to decreased motivation.

Relevance/contribution to research and practice

There exist a large number of papers about useful strategies for technical automation and digitization in production and about the advantages the new technologies. Especially in recent years, numerous publications are about the use of the industrial IoT in modern production and the opportunities of artificial intelligence. However, most of these publications are limited only about the technology and not about possible changes in the use of these novel technologies on the workplaces. In this article, we describe the influence of automation and digitalization in a real case in the semiconductor industry using methods such as observations, expert interviews and other work psychology methods. We researched and introduced a new method to design and introduce HIA. In this way, we are contributing to the emerging literature on human-centric manufacturing (Keil et al., 2020; Lu et al., 2022; Rauch et al., 2020).

From a practical point of view, we showed the need of integrating the perspectives of the affected shop floor workers when automation and digitalization projects in manufacturing are planned in order to be successful.

Summary & Conclusion

Important insights were gained within this work with respect to the positive aspects of the digital transformation of the focus work places at highly automated work areas, but also the fears and risks associated with digitization have been researched (i.e., to enable smooth and intelligent automation, instead of passing through a “valley of tears”). In this way, practical managerial recommendations for actions are derived. With the interviews and the surveys we could find out important points to improve the work in highly automated and digitized work places. One important result was the implementation of a task management, which makes the work easier especially in the maintenance area, so that all employees knows at every time who is working on which tasks. The benefit is, that useless walks can be avoided and all activities are always transparent and well aligned within a team.

Another important result was the use of improved trainings, e.g. trainings that can be performed by new employees themselves based on simulations of the wafer transportation system. At IFD we installed a training for the wafer transportation system with an introduction about all important hardware and software features which can be used as a individual and autonomous learning system. The training can also be used for the certification of the new employees, which saves a lot of time for the experts and reduces the training time for new workers which is very important in a modern factory. At least, one idea was to create a skill and competence management system which helps to visualize always the number of available experts with the individual expert knowledge.

Managing practices are somehow bound to a so called “mechanistic model” which means that employees are used primary as “tools” instead of intelligent human beings with their specific human needs including their fears. This is in the tradition of “block universe thinking”. Within such a worldview, a finite set of physical / chemical laws control each and everything. From a managing perspective, this may lead to a close but false assumption. It may lead to the assumption that if we only know such physical / mechanical laws as far as required, then we can turn off the lights in the factory. In contrary, we have discovered to continuously navigate, monitor, analyze and steer the production system. Because new technologies and methods are brought into the factory on a daily basis, there is continuous need to extend and update existing know how. If we accept this reality, we may characterize the reality (of know-how intense production) not as a block universe, but as a mind universe. The development of this perspective gives grounding motivation for our work and project.

In combination with the fear of loss of the work driven by automation and the loss of personal communication and missing feedback culture a new culture during the work within a factory must be established. This must aim at eliminating the fears of the workers and establishing a culture where the appreciation of the employees is still high and a feedback culture and continuous improvement is always given. The key is a trustful and open communication structure with active feedbacks from employees to managers and managers to employees for continuous improvement of the work and the motivation.

The results of this work also gave rise to important recommendations for action in the creation of new jobs in new factories to be built and also for existing factories. One of the key findings was that, depending on the level of digitization, workplace design can differ from what can be used when building a new factory to what can be used in an existing factory with already

established team structures. The benefits of the new work to the employees is clearly shown and also the fears that can occur, along with recommendations to minimize those fears, e.g. with more appreciation and excellent feedback culture to the people. It is also extremely important that automation and digitization are always controlled by people and that people do not become controlled by the digitization. The results of the work have shown that advancing automation and digitization result in a high level of compression of work tasks that have to be performed by significantly fewer employees and those tasks are getting to be more and more complex. It is therefore important to design digitization applications user-friendly which do not overburden the employees.

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